

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Abdullayev Asqarbek Abduhakimovich

Teacher of SamSIFL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10279040>

Abstract. This article describes about some methodological approaches in teaching English language, it analyzes their role and usage in interaction between teacher and students in the classroom environment.

Keywords: communication skills, motivation, varying teaching materials, co-operative learning, age of acquisition.

Аннотация. В данной статье описываются некоторые методологические подходы в преподавании английского языка, анализируется их роль и использование во взаимодействии учителя и учеников в школьной среде.

Ключевые слова: Навыки общения, мотивация, различные учебные материалы, совместное обучение, возраст приобретения.

In all over the world most of the communication is carried out in English language, as the medium of teaching. As we know that English is comprehensive or worldwide language where the present world is forging ahead by connecting itself to others for fulfilling their harmonious relationships. In English language teaching especially, when English is connected to classroom teaching it plays a very essential role in drawing the students' attention. Of course, at that time, the teacher is centered in the classroom to make a good classroom environment. To create or know good communication skills or to excel in communication skills, one has to acquire expertise in all the four skills. They are listening, verbal communication, interpretation and inscription skills and those skills are so demandable and helpful to have a good relationship between a teacher and students. Before a student acquires with all these skills, he or she has to develop interest towards the subject or the language. In this regard, the teacher plays a very significant role in attracting the student's attention by creating interest among the students. A teacher should play various roles such as a learner to be an example for students to study better, a facilitator to make complicated tasks easier, an assessor to know what levels students are now and make a recognition for students to know objectives to be obtained in the future, a manager to create a good classroom environment and an evaluator to inspire the students. Before teaching the students, a teacher has to first place himself or herself as a learner and think from the learner's outlooking. In doing so, students

can be captured with interest. Additionally, teacher can feel thoughts of students, their lacks and their good sides to learn the subject effectively. This way is so helpful to teach the students efficiently. In the classroom, teacher roles can be discussed with learners as a part of student preparation, along with other characteristics of curriculum. Learners can imagine about what roles they wish for their teacher, how this inclination fits in with other aspects of their learning method, and why the teacher chooses every role. That's why teacher should feel and know what the students are thinking and what is going on in their mind about the lesson. There are also other approaches teacher must pay attention and try to keep his or mind them.

Motivation in the classroom setting plays a very important role. Motivation is one of the most essential factors which influence language learners' success or failure in learning the language. In a teacher's mind, motivated students are usually those who participate actively in class, express interest in the subject-matter, and study a great deal. Teachers can easily recognize characteristics such as these. They also have more opportunity to influence these characteristics than students' reasons for studying the second language or their attitude toward the language and its speakers. If we can make our classrooms places where students enjoy coming because the content is interesting and relevant to their age and level of ability, where the learning goals are challenging yet manageable and clear, and where the atmosphere is supportive and non-threatening, we can make a positive contribution to students' motivation to learn.

Varying the activities, tasks, and materials Students are reassured by the existence of classroom routines which they can depend on. However, lessons which always consist of the same routines, patterns, and formats have been shown to lead to a decrease in attention and an increase in boredom. Varying the activities, tasks, and materials can help to avoid this and increase students' interest levels. Furthermore, varying materials can be understood that to vary the teaching materials help students learn effectively. Because teaching materials are organized according to students' level and during the lesson students can have appropriate materials in conformity with their knowledge.

Using co-operative rather than competitive goals Co-operative learning activities are those in which students must work together in order to complete a task or solve a problem. These techniques have been found to increase the self-confidence of students, including weaker ones, because every participant in a co-

operative task has an important role to play. Knowing that their team-mates are counting on them can increase students' motivation.

There can be other approaches which are effective to teach students but above-mentioned approaches are more preferable to teach students efficiently and they can be used every day lessons. They may illustrate classroom curriculum and help to have greater knowledge on students.

References:

1. Christopher N. Candlin "English language teaching in its social context", London-2001, 368 p.
2. Chris Horner "Creative teaching", USA-2007, 305 p.
3. Abdullayev A. A. THE ROLE OF CLIPPINGS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 145-149.
4. 6. Abdullayev A. A., Khalilova S. THE PART OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION //THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 60-65.
5. 7. Abdullayev A. A. THE ROLE OF TRANSLATION IN TEACHING FL //International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor. – 2023. – Т. 7. – №. 2. – С. 1.
6. 8. Obidjonovna M. F. SOME TEACHING PRINCIPLES OF READING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 23. – №. 1. – С. 18-20.
7. Исмаилов А. Вопрос формирования педагогической культуры в современной методике преподавания иностранных языков //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 2 (79). – С. 49-56.
8. Ismailov A. R. STYLISTIC AND PRAGMATIC ASPECT IN DISCOURSE ANALYSIS //Wschodnioeuropejskie Czasopismo Naukowe. – 2018. – №. 4-4. – С. 62-65.
9. Ismailov A. R. THE PROBLEM OF THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE IN MODERN METHODICS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES //Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. – 2021. – №. 4-8. – С. 46-49.
10. Ismailov A., Nasrullaev J. The use of audiovisual devices in teaching technical courses in english //Science and practice: a new level of integration in the modern world. – 2019. – С. 147-150.

11. Rustomovich D. I. A. et al. The role of verbal and non-verbal communication in learning foreign language //World Bulletin of Social Sciences. – 2022. – T. 9. – C. 10-11.
12. www.researchgate.net

